

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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QANDLI DIABET KELIB CHIQISH MEXANIZMI VA PATALOGIYASI

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Annotatsiya: Qandli diabet (Diabetes mellitus) bu organizmdagi uglevodlar, yog'lar va oqsillar almashinuvining buzulishi bilan kechadigan surunkali kasallik bo'lib, u insulin gormoni yetishmovchiligi yoki to'qimalarning insulinga sezgirligi pasayishi natijasida rivojlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Diabetes mellitus*, metabolik, geterogen, giperglikemiya, otoim-mun, insulin terapiyasi, metformin

Kirish. Qandli diabet- insulin sekretarining yetarli darajada yoki samarasiz javob berishi natijasida kelib chiqadigan metabolik kasallik bo'lib, u qon glyukoza darajasining oshishi (giperglikemiya) bilan tavsiflanadi. Qandli diabet sindromlarning geterogen guruhidir. Glyukoza organizm uchun asosiy energiya manbai bo'lib, qandli diabet holatida glyukoza nazorati tartibsiz bo'ladi. Qandli diabetda giperglikemiya boshlanishida uchta asosiy nuqson mavjud, ya'ni jigarda gkyukoza ishlab chiqarishning ko'payishi, insulin sekretsiasining pasayishi va insulin ta'sirining buzulishi.

Hannah Sokolayam Ibrahim va boshqa olimlarning tadqiqotlariga e'tibor qaratadigan bo'lsak, qandli diabetni turlarini o'rganishgan va uni uchta asosiy tur borligini aniqlashgan. 1-toifa diabet, 2-toifa diabet va homiladorlik diabeti (homiladorlik bilan bog'liq diabet). 1-toifa diabet insulin yetishmovchiligi va natijasida giperglikemiya bilan belgilanadigan otoimmun kasallikdir. Bu butun dunyo bo'ylab bir nechta odamlarga ta'sir qiladi va yurak-qon tomir va buyrak kasalliklari, ko'rish qobilyatini yo'qotish kabi kasalliklarga chalinadi. 1-toifa diabetni davolashning umumiy usuli bu insulin terapiyasi hisoblanadi. 2-toifa diabet keng tarqalgan metabolitik kasallik bo'lib, u oshqozon osti bezining b-hujatralari tomonidan insulin yetishmovchiligi va to'qimalarning insulinga to'g'ri javob bera olmasligi natijasida yuzaga keladi. Ushbu kasallik uchun xavf omillari qon glyukoza darajasi, semizlik, noto'g'ri ovqalanish, qarish, stress va depresiya hisoblanadi. 2-toifa diabetni davolash va boshqarish uchun metformin va boshqa glyukoza tushuruvchi vositalar bilan birgalikda insulin terapiyasi talab qilinadi. Gestatsion diabet (homiladorlik bilan bog'liq diabet) bu homilador ayolning yuqori qon shakariga ega bo'lgan holat. Ba'zi ayollarda faqat homiladorlik paytida paydo bo'ladi va onaga ham, bolaga ham ta'sir qilishi mumkin. Bu semizlik, oilaviy diabet va onaning yoshi kabi bir qator omillar qo'zg'atadi. Insulin terapiyasi va turmush tarzini o'zgartirish orqali davolanadi.

Zakiya Safarova va Sharofat Shamsiyevalarning tadqiqotlariga e'tibor bersak ular asosan oshqozon bezini 2% gina sekretorlik vazifasini bajaruvchi qismni o'rganishgan.

Sekretorlik vazifasiga ko'ra oshqozon osti bezi hujayralari 5 ta asosiy turlari ajratiladi: Insulin sintez qiluvchi beta hujayralar – 60-80% Glukogon ishlab chiqaradigan alfa hujayralar – 20-30 % Somatostatin hosil qiluvchi Delta hujayralari -8% ni D1-vipni chaqiradigan hujayralar Vazoaktiv intestinal polipeptid -0,5 % ni tashkil qiladi.

Birinchi turdagi qandli diabet – bu kasallikning rivojlanishida katta rol o'ynaydi. Kasallikka genetik moslashuv ayrim genlarning xromosomalarida mavjudligi bilan belgilanadi, bu asosan salbiy ekologik omillar ta'siri ostida namoyon bo'ladi.

Ikkinchi turdagi qandli diabet sabablari. Qandli diabet kasalligining ikkinchi turi 90% gacha, turmush tarzi va ovqatlanish tabiati bilan chambarchas bog'liq, aniqrog'i ortiqcha vazn va gipodinamiya bilan bog'liq. Ikkinchi turdagi diabet qanday rivojlanadi? Insulin tananing mushak, yog' va jigar hujayralari tomonidan glyukoza ishlatilishini rag'batlantiradi. Agar bu hujayralarning insulunga sezgirligi kamaysa, qondagi glyukoza miqdori ko'tariladi, bu vaqtni o'tishi bilan ikkinchi turdagi diabetga olib keladi.

Homilador ayollar, homiladorlik qandli diabetning sabablari. Homiladorlik qandli diabet homiladorlik davrida birinchi marta qon glyukoza darajasining oshishi aniqlangan holatni anglatadi. Bu juda kam uchraydi va kasallikning barcha shakllarining 4% ni tashkil qiladi.

Ko'pincha qandli diabet homiladorlikning ikkinchi yarmini o'rtalarida ya'ni 24-28 hafta ichida aniqlanadi. Uning rivojlanishi homiladorlik garmonlarining ta'siri bilan bog'liq bo'lib, organizm hujayralarining insulin ta'siriga sezuvchanligini kamaytiradi, ya'ni insulin qarshiligiga olib keladi.

Tahlillar shuni ko'rsatdiki:

10 yoshdan 39 yoshgacha bo'lgan bemorlar umumiy kasallarning 8-10% ini, bular asosan 1983-2004 yillar oralig'ida tug'ilgan bemorlar ; 40 yoshdan yuqorilar 90-92 % ni, bular 1980 – yildan yuqorilar. Sabablari ham albatta turlicha: 30% bemorlarda nasldan naslga o'tishda, 40% bemorlarda turli tashqi omillar natijasida, 30% notu'g'ri ovqatlanish, hamda 10% gipodinamiya.

Xulosa: Ushbu maqolada biz qandli diabet genetik, ekologik va turmush tarzi omillarning murakkab o'zaro ta'siridan kelib chiqadi degan xulosaga keldik. Shunday qilib qandli diabet kasalligi aynan ma'lum bir virus yoki aynan ma'lum bir sabab tufayli yuzaga kelmaydi, birinchi o'rinda kundalik rejimni to'g'ri tashkil qilish va faol sog'lom hayot tarziga ega bo'lish talab etiladi.

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